

Acetoacetanilide Chelates of Titanium (IV)*

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Three types of acetoacetanilide chelates of titanium (IV) have been isolated—the trichloro mono-(acetoacetanilidato)-titanium (IV), dichloro-bis (acetoacetanilidato) titanium (IV), and the monochloro tris (acetoacetanilidato) titanium (IV). The monobromo-and the monoiodo tris-(acetoacetanilidato) titanium (IV) chelates have been also isolated.

Addition compounds of titanium (IV) halides with acetoacetanilide have been prepared and characterised. Infrared spectral data on acetoacetanilide chelates of titanium (IV) are also presented.

Replacement of a single chlorine atom from dichlorobis (acetylacetonato) titanium (IV) leading to the isolation of tris (acetoacetanilidato) titanium (IV) has already been reported by us¹. The syntheses of monobromo-and monoiodo-tris (acetoacetanilidato) titanium (IV) have now been effected from dibromo-and diiodo bis (acetylacetonato) titanium (IV) respectively.

Another approach towards the preparation of the monochloro and monobromo-chelates, through their addition compounds has also been made. We wish to report the result of our studies on these complexes in this communication.

EXPERIMENTAL

Titanium tetrachloride was purified and distilled before use. Titanium tetrabromide and tetraiodide were prepared according to the procedure of Brauer². Dichloro bis (acetylacetonato) titanium (IV) was prepared by the reaction between titanium tetrachloride and acetylacetone in benzene according to the procedure of Doron.³ All the solvents employed were purified before use.

T. G. A. was carried out in a balance using McBain-Bakr type Quartz spring⁴ having a sensitivity of 2.5 mg. per millimeter extension. About 25 mg. of the sample is required for the investigation.

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2. Brauer, G. "Handbook of Preparative Inorganic Chemistry", Vol. II, 2nd Edn. p. 1201. 1205. Academic Press, New York (1965).
3. V. Doron, *Inorganic Syntheses*, 1963, 7, 50.
4. L., Singh, *J. Sci. Industr. Res.*, 1952, 11A, 63.

The extension of the spring was measured with a travelling microscope every two minutes. while the temperature of the furnace was increased at a constant rate of about 4° per minute. The samples were heated in air.

X-ray diffraction data were obtained from powder patterns, using molybdenum target (Zr-filter), 50 KV 20 ma filament current and 3 hr. exposure time.

Dibromo bis (acetylacetonato) titanium (IV): Titanium tetrabromide (3.5 g ; 0.01 mole) in dry benzene (50 ml.) was mixed with excess of acetylacetone in benzene (20 ml.) and refluxed till the reaction was complete (4 hr.). More than half the benzene was removed by distillation. After cooling, the separated brown solid was filtered under nitrogen atmosphere and dried under vacuum. Yield 2.2 g ; 54.2%.

Found ; C, 30.12 ; H, 3.42 ; Br, 39.02 ; Ti, 11.47%.

Calc. for $C_{10}H_{14}O_4Br_2 Ti$: C, 29.59 ; H, 3.48 ; Br, 39.39 ; Ti, 11.80%.

Diiodo bis (acetylacetonato) titanium (IV): The deep reddish-brown semi-solid obtained essentially in the above manner was poured into petroleum ether (60-80). The solid was collected on a filter under suction and washed with two 10 ml. portions of petroleum ether and dried under vacuum. Yield. 95%.

Found : C, 25.04 ; H, 3.05 ; I, 51.13 ; Ti, 9.39%.

Calc. for $C_{10}H_{14}O_4I_2 Ti$: C, 24.03 ; H, 2.82 ; I, 50.79 ; Ti, 9.59%.

Monobromo tris (acetoacetanilidato) titanium (IV): Dibromo bis (acetylacetonato) titanium (IV) (1.22 g ; 0.003 mole) in benzene (50 ml.) and acetoacetanilide (1.59 g ; 0.009 mole) in benzene (20 ml.) were mixed together and refluxed for 3 hr. The orange-red solid was collected on a filter under suction, washed twice with 5 ml. portions of benzene and dried under vacuum, Yield, 2.0 g ; 91.4%. m. p. 211-12°.

Found : C, 55.08 ; H, 4.78 ; Br, 13.05 ; N, 5.67 ; Ti, 7.1%.

Calc. for $C_{30}H_{30}O_6N_3 BrTi$: C, 54.88 ; H, 4.61 ; Br, 12.77 ; N, 6.40 ; Ti, 7.30%.

Monoiodo tris (acetoacetanilidato) titanium (IV): Diiodo bis (acetylacetonato) titanium (IV) (1.25 g ; 0.0025 mole) in benzene (50 ml.) and acetoacetanilide (1.33 g ; 0.0075 mole) in benzene (20 ml.) were mixed together and refluxed for 6 hr. The reddish-brown solid was collected on a filter under suction, washed with 5 ml. portions of benzene, and dried under vacuum. Yield 1.6 g ; 77%. m. p. 218°.

Found : C, 44.10 ; H, 3.44 ; N, 5.2 ; Ti, 5.32 ; I 31.06%

Calc. for $C_{30}H_{31}O_6N_3 I_2$: C, 43.30 ; H, 3.64 ; N, 5.06 ; Ti, 5.76 ; I, 30.50%.

$TiCl_4 \cdot 3HacacN$: Titanium tetrachloride (0.95 g ; 0.005 mole) in chloroform (20 ml.) was added dropwise to a solution of acetoacetanilide (2.66 g ; 0.015 mole) in chloroform (30 ml). Immediately, a deep red solution was obtained. Addition of petroleum ether precipitated the orange-red compound. It was collected on a filter

under suction, washed with two 5 ml. portions of petroleum ether and dried under vacuum at room temperature. Yield, 2.9 ; 80.34%.

Found : N, 5.70 ; Ti, 6.39 ; Cl, 20.6%.

Calc. For $C_{80}H_{83}O_6N_3 TiCl_4$: N, 5.83 ; Ti, 6.64 ; Cl, 19.65%.

$TiCl_4 \cdot 3HacacN$ on heating at 140° for 8 hr. yielded a reddish brown product almost identical with monochlorotris (acetoacetanilidato) titanium reported earlier⁷.

Found ; C, 85.26 ; H, 5.47 ; N, 7.3%.

$C_{80}H_{80}O_6N_3 Cl Ti$ requires C, 58.86 ; H, 4.93 ; N, 6.87%.

$TiBr_4 \cdot 3HacacN$: Titanium tetrabromide (3.68 g ; 0.01 mole) in chloroform (40 ml.) and acetoacetanilide (5.32 g ; 0.03 mole) in the same solvent (30 ml.) were mixed together at room temperature. Immediately a deep red solution was obtained. Addition of petroleum ether ($60-80^\circ$) precipitated a deep red solid which was collected on a filter under suction, washed with petroleum ether and dried under vacuum.

Yield, 7.5 g ; 83.4%.

Found : N, 4.80 ; Ti, 5.45 ; Br, 34.48%.

Calc. for $C_{80}H_{83}O_6N_3 TiBr_4$: N, 4.67 ; Ti, 5.33 ; Br, 35.55%.

Trichloromono (acetoacetanilidato) titanium (IV) : Titanium tetrachloride (2.85 g ; 0.015 mole) in benzene (30 ml.) and acetoacetanilide (1.77 g ; 0.01 mole) in benzene (20 ml.) were mixed together at 0° and then refluxed for 4 hr. The reddish-brown product separated on cooling was collected on a filter under suction and washed with benzene and dried under vacuum. Yield, 3.0 g ; 60.60%.

Found : N, 4.4 ; Ti, 13.98 ; Cl, 31.50%.

Calc. for $C_{10}H_{10}O_2N. TiCl_3$: N, 4.24 ; Ti, 14.49 ; Cl, 32.20%.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Instances of replacement of chlorine atoms in titanium tetrachloride by a β -dicarbonyl compound leading to trichloro^{5,6,7} or dichloro⁵⁻⁹ chelates are well known. However, the replacement of three halogen atoms in titanium tetrahalides by three β -dicarbonyl functions leading to the isolation of monohalogeno titanium (IV) chelates is now found to be feasible. However, elemental analysis indicated the presence of one hydrogen iodide molecule attached to the monoiodotris

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(acetoacetanilidato) titanium (IV), TGA curves (fig. 1) for the three compounds are

Fig. 1.

almost identical except for a break in the monoiodo compound at 230°. At this temperature the loss in weight (table I) for the monoiodo compound (14.69%) corresponds nearly to the loss of one molecule of HI. It can be seen that there is considerable

TABLE I

Percentage weight loss of monohalogeno tris (acetoacetanilidato) titanium (IV) compounds (190-310°), heating rate in air 4°/min

Temperature °C	Ti (acacN) ₃ Cl	Ti (acacN) ₃ Br	Ti (acacN) ₃ I. HI
190	6.39	3.77	2.45
200	7.38	4.24	2.45
210	16.71	7.54	3.42
220	26.56	17.89	7.35
230	35.40	28.25	14.69
235	36.39	30.13	18.58
240	37.37	30.53	19.59
250	42.29	31.08	20.57
270	45.24	32.03	23.51
300	49.17	35.31	30.37
310	50.16	35.79	33.31

decomposition at this temperature (230°) for the monochloro compound (35.4%) and the monobromo compound (28.25%) as indicated by the percentage losses. From the thermal analysis data it appears that the monoiodo compound is more stable than the monobromo compound or the monochloro compound.

X-ray powder pattern data for monobromo and monoiodo compounds are given in table II, the data for monochloro compound have already been reported¹.

TABLE II
X-Ray diffraction data of monobromo-and monoiodo tris-
(acetoacetanilidato)-titanium (IV) complexes.

Monobromo tris (acetoacetanilidato)-titanium (IV) Ti (acacN) ₃ Br		Monoiodo tris (acetoacetanilidato) Titanium (IV) Ti (acacN) ₃ I.HI.	
'd' values (Å)	Intensity %	'd' values (Å)	Intensity %
2.06	100	2.0	100
2.965	100	2.74	100
3.58	40-50	3.28	40
3.995	40-50	3.84	80-90
4.36	80	4.18	40-50
4.83	80-90	4.445	20
5.135	80-90	4.885	20
5.395	70	5.30	20
6.26	100	5.52	90
6.620	100	5.875	90
7.285	50	6.08	10-20
7.53	20-30	6.45	"
7.64	20	6.60	"
7.85	10-20	6.865	"

The infrared absorption maxima in nujol mull of monochloro, monobromo-and monoiodo-tris (acetoacetanilidato) titanium (IV) chelates together with the dichloro-bis (acetoacetanilidato) titanium (IV) and trichloro mono (acetoacetanilidato) titanium (IV) are presented in table III. As in the case of acetoacetanilide chelates with

TABLE III

Infrared absorption frequencies (cm⁻¹) of titanium (IV) chelates in nujol mull.

Ti (acacN)Cl ₃	Ti (acacN) ₂ Cl ₂	Ti (acacN) ₃ Cl	Ti (acacN) ₃ Br	Ti (acacN) ₃ I.HI	Possible assignments.
3250m	3311m	3185w	3030w	3226m	NH str.
2900*b, vs	2924*b, vs	2924*b, s	2890*b, s	3106m	
1660m	—	—	—	2890*b, s	
1600s	1617s	1617s	1608s	1608s	C=C+amide I
1575vs	1587vs	1597vs	1587vs	1587s	C=C str. +C=O str.
1550vs	1558vs	1567vs	1558vs	1558vs	Amide II
149)sh	1493vs	1502vs	1493vs	1493vs	Phenyl vibration
1460*vs	1457vs	1458vs	1449vs	1449vs	
—	—	—	—	1433sh	CH ₂ deg. def.
—	1401s	1401s	1401s	1401s	
1375*vs	1377*s	1381*s	1377*s	1377*s	
—	1333s	—	—	—	
1310s	1319s	1319s	1326s	1326s	
1300sh	1299w	1302m	1312s	1312s	Amide III
—	—	—	1299m	—	
1240s	1247b, s	1253s	1250s	1247s	
—	1229w	1229m	—	1229m	
1175s	1182s	1182s	1188s	1178s	CH in plane def.
1080w	1085w	1085w	1080w	1080w	
1040s	1348s	1046s	1044s	1044s	
1025s	—	1031m	1027m	1027m	
—	998w	1002w	1002w	1002w	
—	978s	—	—	—	
970b, s	967b, vs	971b, vs	971b, vs	971b, vs	
910m	910m	905w	901w	901w	
810m	796b, s	—	808m	787b, m	
780m	780m	784b, m	—	—	
760b, s	757b, vs	752b, m	797b, m	752b, m	CH O. P. def.
725b,m	—	—	—	734m	
685b, m	687b, vs	688b, m	688b, m	686b, m	Mono substitution, Ring Def+MO Str.

Cu (II), Be (II), Al (III), Cr (III) and Fe (III) previously reported by us¹⁰ the carbonyl absorption of the ligand at 1727 cm^{-1} is shifted on chelation to much lower frequencies. This band can be located in the Ti (IV) chelates at ca. 1580 cm^{-1} . The amide II and III bands can be located at ca. 1550 cm^{-1} and at ca. 1300 cm^{-1} . The bands present at ca. 1180 cm^{-1} in all the chelates can be ascribed to C-H in plane bending mode.

In the monohalogeno tris (acetoacetanilidato) titanium (IV) complexes, if all the acetoacetanilide groups are bidentate, a coordination number of seven for titanium is implied. That all the groups are bidentate is confirmed by the infrared spectra which are similar to the spectra of other complexes of acetoacetanilide with Cu (II), Be (II), Al (III), Cr (III) and Fe (III). Some difference would be expected if one or more ligands were unidentate. The position of absorption bands (table IV) in the infrared

TABLE IV

Infrared absorption frequencies (cm^{-1}) of titanium (IV) chelates in nujol mull.

Ti (acac) ₃ Br ₃	Ti (acac) ₃ I ₃	Possible assignments
2950*b, vs	2950*b, vs	
1530sh	1530sh	
1525vs	1520vs	C=O str.
1510s	1515vs	C=C str.
1480*s	1460*s	
1440 s	1423m	CH ₃ def. (asym)
1390m	—	
1380*s	1370*s	
	1340s	CH ₃ def (sym)
1320vs	1310s	C-O str.
1300sh	1280s	C-C str.
1040vs	1025s	
1030sh	1010w	
955m	950w	
940s	935s	
820s	825m	CH O. P. def.
—	810w	
780w	795m	
—	730s	
680s	680s	

spectra of the dibromo and diiodo (acetylacetonato) titanium (IV), not reported before, is similar to that of the bands in dichloro-bis (acetylacetonato) titanium (IV) recently reported¹¹.

In the addition compounds there is a metal to oxygen bond formation as evidenced in the infrared spectra (Table V) by an appreciable negative shift¹²⁻¹⁴ of

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13. B., Mori, J. Göhring, D. Cassimatis, and B. P. Susz, *Helv. Chim. Acta*, 1962 45.77.
14. D. Cassimatis, and B. P. Susz, *Helv. Chim. Acta*, 1960, 43. 852.

TABLE V

The infrared absorption frequencies (cm^{-1}) in nujol mull of titanium tetrahalide adducts with acetoacetanilide

Acetoacetanilide (HacacN)	$\text{TiCl}_4 \cdot 3\text{HacacN}$	$\text{TiBr}_4 \cdot 3\text{HacacN}$
3268s	—	—
3145w	3200vw	3200w
3067s, sh	—	—
2924*vs, b	2900*b, vs	2900*b, vs
1946m	—	—
1873m	—	—
1727vs	1600s	1600s
1661vs	1575s	1580s
1597vs	1550s	1550s
1538b, vs	—	1500s
	1470sh	—
1466*s	1450*s	1450*b, vs
1449vs	—	—
1377*s	1370 [~] s	1370*vs
1346w	—	—
1316s	1309s	1310s
	—	1300sh
1279m	—	—
1238s	1245s	1250s
	1225sh	—
1168vs	1175s	1175s
1080s	1075vw	1080vw
1027W	1040s	1040s
1006m	1030m	1025m
967s	965s, b	970b, vs
905s	—	910
868s	—	—
821w	—	800b, w
757b, vs	750m, b	750b, m
740s	—	—
708w	—	—
691b, vs	690m, b	685 b, m

*Nujol peaks

s, strong ; m, medium ; w, weak ; v, very ; b, broad ; sh, shoulder.

the carbonyl stretching frequency. The 1 : 3 adduct between TiCl_4 and acetoacetanilide on heating yielded a reddish brown product with m.p. 216° . The infrared spectrum and elemental analysis showed this to be monochloro tris (acetoacetanilidato) titanium (IV). The titanium tetrabromide adduct, however, remained unchanged when heated at 140° for several hours.